

ACTIVITY REGARDING APPLICATION OF THERMOPLASTIC FRP TO JAPANESE INFRASTRUCTURE

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ABSTRACT

The Japanese Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science, and Technology started the Center of Innovation program (COI project). The final outcome of this project is the social implementation of seeds technology developed based on the country's needs. Our Innovative Composite Materials Research and Development Center promotes "construction of the next-generation infrastructure system by innovative composite materials" as a COI project. Herein "Innovative composite materials" includes thermoplastic fiber reinforced plastics. Therefore, seeds technology such as biotechnology, polymer chemistry, fiber engineering, and mechanical engineering are harmonized, and are applied to the sites of social infrastructure, housing infrastructure, and marine infrastructure on the basis of their needs. The "Research group for the approach to the civil engineering field of innovative composite materials" was established to investigate the application needs for social infrastructure. Front-line clients (administrators), builders, manufacturers, and evaluation certifiers participate to investigate appropriate infrastructures for the utilization of innovative materials, and propose requirement specifications. As a result, light weight, high durability, water blocking, and ease of shaving and cutting were cited as FRP features. Additionally COI project will conduct the following research: (1) LCC including the material cost, construction cost, and maintenance cost; (2) durability under severe environment conditions for a long time; (3) manufacturing and processing; (4) thermal expansion coefficient; and (5) earthquake resistance.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Current status of Japanese infrastructure

Reinforced concrete and steel have been used in numerous infrastructures as inexpensive construction materials. Over the years, these constructions have provided immeasurable benefits to our lives. In Japan, the number of structures older than 50 years is increasing rapidly, which means that the construction materials used in these structures have also aged. In particular, deterioration due to chloride attack has increased. Picture 1 shows the pier of a reinforced concrete bridge located on the coast line and Picture 2 shows the beam of a reinforced concrete bridge. As shown in these pictures, in the Hokuriku region where we live, because there are high levels of airborne salt in winter, deterioration in reinforced concrete structures occurs within 20–30 years.

There are several reinforcement methods for concrete structures, such as the stringer expansion method, top up thickness method, and steel plate bonding method. Among them, reinforcement with fiber reinforced plastic (FRP winding stand method and FRP bond method) has attracted attention in recent years, even in the structural civil engineering field in Japan. For example, the composite structure committee in Japan Society of Civil Engineers (JSCE) has promoted "investigation and research of assignments," "drafting and updating of guidelines and standards for design, construction, and maintenance," "holding seminars, symposia, lectures, and site tours," "research cooperation with domestic and international academic societies and related organizations," "editing of publications,"

and “planning for medium-term and long-term research on composite materials and structures.” Till date, 20 research subcommittees have been established, and 14 reports published, as listed in Table 1. Unfortunately there are few achievements.

Picture 1: Situation of flying salt on a pier of a reinforced concrete coastal bridge from the sea.

Picture 2: Deteriorated beam of a reinforced concrete bridge near the coast.

Title	Date
Advanced Technology for Hybrid Structures -Methods and Applications for Civil Engineering Structures-	July, 2007
Guidelines for Design and Construction of FRP Footbridges	Jan, 2011
Basic Theory and Design of Hybrid Structures	March, 2012
Guidelines for Design and Construction of FRP Hydraulic Gates	Feb, 2014
Survey and Analysis on the Current Situation of Hybrid Structures -Toward the Advancement of a Performance-Based Design Method for Hybrid Structures-	July, 2008
Characteristics of Various Materials and Performance Evaluation of New Hybrid Structures -Analysis of Construction Methods by Marketing Technique-	July, 2008
Case-Based Current Assessment on Maintenance Technologies for Hybrid Structures	May, 2010
Advanced Technology of Repair and Strengthening of Steel Structures Using Externally - Bonded FRP Composites	June, 2012
Advanced Technology of Hybrid Structures Using Resin Materials	June, 2012
Current Status of Waterproofing and Drainage Technologies for Hybrid Structures	July, 2013
Problems and Possibilities of Hybrid Structures Against a Large Earthquake	July, 2013
Advanced Technologies of Joining for FRP Structures and FRP Bonding for Steel Structures	Nov, 2013
Basic Data for the Design of Structural FRP for Construction	Nov, 2014
Current Trends and Future Issues for Design Code for Upgrading Concrete Structures with Use of FRP	Nov, 2014

Table 1: Reports published by the JSCE composite structure committee.

1.2 Activity by COI project

The Japanese Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science, and Technology started the Center of Innovation program (hereinafter, the COI project), so that a good standard of living is maintained even after 10 years [1]. The project envisions the following: (1) securing sustainability as a developed country with a declining birthrate and aging population; (2) construction of a rich living environment

(toward a prosperous and respected country); and (3) construction of a durable society with vigor. The future of this program is to advance innovative research and development by cooperating with industry and academia. Twelve themes were selected in October, 2013, and they will run until March, 2022. The final outcome of the study is the social implementation of seeds technology developed based on the country's needs.

The Innovative Composite Materials Research and Development Center (hereinafter, the ICC) at the Kanazawa Institute of Technology (KIT) promotes “construction of the next-generation infrastructure system by innovative composite materials – realization of multi-century societies that can coexist with the earth safely and securely” as a project in the third vision. “Innovative composite materials” includes thermoplastic fiber reinforced plastics (FRTP). Therefore, seeds technology such as biotechnology, polymer chemistry, fiber engineering, and mechanical engineering are harmonized, and are applied to the sites of social infrastructure, housing infrastructure, and marine infrastructure on the basis of their needs. The image of the construction of a next-generation infrastructure system using this innovative material is shown in Figure 1. Social infrastructure, such as tunnels and bridges; housing infrastructure, such as skyscrapers; and marine infrastructure, such as large sailing ships and sea windmills are the targets.

Figure 1: Construction of next-generation infrastructure system with innovative materials.

2 NEEDS INVESTIGATION OF FRTP FOR SOCIAL INFRASTRUCTURE

2.1 Investigation procedure

The “Research group for the approach to the civil engineering field of innovative composite materials” (hereinafter, the research group) was established to investigate the application needs for social infrastructure in October, 2014. The committee meets every three months, alternating between Tokyo and the ICC, as shown in Picture 3.

Front-line clients (administrators), builders, manufacturers, and evaluation certifiers participate in this research group. Many needs and requirement specifications are proposed by technical experts at various positions, according to the schedule in Table 2. In addition, the KIT-COI project members specializing in material and forming participate temporarily, and information between different fields is exchanged.

Picture 3: Research group committee.

No.	Timing	Place	Contents
1	October, 2014	Tokyo	Description of the schedule and arrangements of the merits and demerits of innovative composite materials.
2	January, 2015	Kanazawa	Enumeration of infrastructure that can utilize high tensile strength, high durability, and light weight, considering the cost of innovative composite materials.
3	June, 2015	Tokyo	
4	August, 2015	Kanazawa	Detailed inspection of structures that can be diverted to innovative composite materials.
5	October, 2015	Tokyo	1) Arrangement of specification and shape. 2) Arrangement of the material cost considering life cycle cost (LCC).
6	February, 2015	Kanazawa	Examination of future development plans.

Table 2: Research group schedule.

2.2 Content of the investigation

This research group has met twice, and appropriate infrastructures for the utilization of innovative materials were investigated. As a result, light weight, high durability, water blocking, and ease of shaving and cutting were cited as FRP features. For example, it is possible to build without using heavy equipment if the materials are lightweight. In addition, light weight results in cost reduction when transporting to an isolated island, as a large amount of material can be carried at the same time. Further, it is possible to carry smaller parts and assemble them at the construction site, because thermoplastic FRP is capable of fusion bonding in contrast to thermosetting FRP. Besides, even if delamination occurs, it is possible to maintain the same performance by performing a weld joint repair.

3 FUTURE RESEARCH CHALLENGES

KIT-COI project will conduct the following research to appropriately use innovative materials for infrastructure.

3.1 Life cycle cost (LCC)

Numerous infrastructures are public structures constructed and maintained by tax revenue. Therefore, it is necessary to economize their cost.

Here, thermosetting FRP is used to strengthen a bridge as shown in Picture 4. However, it is not yet generally used because the cost is high. If thermoplastic FRP is used instead, productivity is increased and the cost can be reduced.

Structures that are built with innovative materials increase the initial cost compared to reinforced concrete structures or steel structures. However, it is possible to reduce the maintenance cost in service because innovative materials have high durability against chloride attack.

On the basis of these examples, the LCC of structures constructed by innovative materials is evaluated, including the material cost, construction cost, and maintenance cost.

Picture 4: Strengthening of bridge by a thermosetting FRP plate.

3.2 Durability

Infrastructures are exposed to severe environment conditions for a long time, sometimes for over 100 years. These environmental factors include temperature extremes (from -20 to 80 °C), wet and dry weather cycles (50 RH% to 95 RH%), and ultraviolet rays. Under these circumstances, the strength, fatigue and creep properties of innovative composite materials are evaluated for a life span of 100 years.

3.3 Manufacturing and processing

“Arbitrary shape” or “same shape” is required for infrastructures, even in the case of using FRP. Here, “arbitrary shape” is necessary to perform repair or strengthening of existing structures in various shapes. “Same shape” is necessary to make guardrails and scaffolding plates, regardless of the construction site.

Furthermore, a large-scale structure is built from thermoplastic parts connected by heat at the site. Therefore, it is necessary that the durability and structural performance are evaluated at the connection points.

3.4 Thermal expansion coefficient

The thermal expansion coefficient of concrete is $1.0 (10^{-5}/^{\circ}\text{C})$. In addition, the thermal expansion coefficient of steel is $1.2 (10^{-5}/^{\circ}\text{C})$. Therefore both values are approximately equal. As a result, a change of the temperature does not cause a gap inside the reinforced concrete structure.

However, the thermal expansion coefficient of carbon fiber is 0 to $0.01 (10^{-5}/^{\circ}\text{C})$. If Carbon-FRTP is combined with reinforced concrete, a gap is caused by a change in the outside air temperature. Therefore, when an innovative material is integrated with concrete and steel, its thermal expansion coefficient is required to be in the 1.0 – $1.2 (10^{-5}/^{\circ}\text{C})$ range. Further, the adhesion strength between the innovative composite materials and concrete or steel is evaluated under several temperatures.

3.5 Earthquake resistance

Multiple earthquakes have occurred in Japan, including the Great East Japan earthquake on March 11, 2011. Concrete is strong against compression and steel is strong against tension. In addition, each material has a plastic region, leading to earthquake resistance. However, FRP manufactured from a single material is a perfect elastic body without any plastic region [2]. Therefore, high plastic performance is expected for innovative composite materials.

When a concrete specimen was pasted with a thermosetting FRP sheet with single carbon fiber, the sheet ruptured and was destroyed brittlely as shown in Picture 5. On the other hand, when a concrete specimen was pasted with a thermosetting FRP sheet with composite materials of carbon fiber and

high-strength polyethylene fibers, the sheet was stripped from the end and was destroyed for toughness without exploding as shown in Picture 6 [3].

Picture 5: Destruction state of concrete pasted thermosetting FRP sheet with single carbon fiber.

Picture 6: Destruction state of concrete pasted thermosetting FRP sheet with composite materials of carbon fiber and high-strength polyethylene fibers.

4 CONCLUDING REMARKS

In this paper, research activity on infrastructure application of thermoplastic FRP in Japan was described with an introduction to the KIT-COI project. The advantages of FRP include light weight and high corrosion resistance. In addition, the cost of thermoplastic FRP will be one-third that of conventional thermosetting FRP. The study of thermoplastic FRP utilization in future infrastructure is promoted, taking into account the reduction in cost.

In Japan, many civil engineering structures were constructed in the 1960s. Because 50 years have passed since then, the progression of aging and a lack of earthquake resistance in these structures has become a problem. These need removal and renewal, or repair and reinforcement. Therefore, these days, renewal structures are designed considering that the life cycle, or the repair and strengthening of existing structures is increasing. As a result of the KIT-COI project, we hope that the developed thermoplastic FRP contributes to a realization of safe infrastructure, and its construction or upgrade of existing structures.

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